

The Microbial Transformation of Organic Compounds*

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During contact with organic substances, the microbial cell is most often influenced in its growth and, reversely, causes numerous changes in organic substances through its enzyme systems. The cell can utilize many organic compounds by cleavage to obtain energy, others as building material necessary for its own biosynthetic processes, and finally converts further substances by detoxication mechanism. The given examples include co-oxidation, co-metabolism, enzyme induction, detoxication, and utilization of reactions for preparative purposes and in the chemotaxonomy of microbes. These examples state in the first place papers in the field of the metabolism of sugars and steroids related to stereospecific conversions of organic compounds by microbial enzymes that have been carried out in the Research Institute for Pharmacy and Biochemistry in Prague. An outline of the future development is given featuring the use of microbial spore enzymes and microbial enzymes bound in the solid phase on carriers.

THE most part of the metabolism of any microbial cell is concerned with the utilization of carbon compounds. Microbes oxidize such substances mainly as a source of energy.^{2,1} It is generally believed that only a small proportion of the products resulting from such dissimilations is transformed into cellular plasm. Microorganisms can attack every known carbon compound.^{3,8,4,9} Since most of those compounds in natural environment of microorganism can be expected to undergo both acute fluctuation and gradual profound shifts, it would seem that successful competition by a species should depend not only on its range of phenotypic *adaptability* but also on the *flexibility of its genetic apparatus* for the acquisition or deletion of metabolic functions. Such *genetic alterations* might arise either from mutational events or from recombination with foreign genomes. Many examples of mutations show, that then a microorganism is able to utilize new resources. New metabolic pathways must be built stepwise and grafted onto preexisting metabolic network.^{4,7}

From biochemical viewpoint the reactions of organic compounds catalyzed by microbial enzymes can be divided into three categories: ^{3,6,3,7}

1. Reactions which cleave substrates, connected with energetic yield.
2. Biosynthetic reactions with energy consumption.
3. Transformations of non-obligatory organic compounds, in which the energetic relations are not important for microbial cells and have rather "detoxication" significance.

Two first types determine the microbial growth and reproduction, the third one is independent on the

microbial growth. The processes in which a microorganism oxidized a substance without being able to utilize the energy derived from this oxidation to support growth, were named "*Co-oxidations*" and later more general term "*Co-metabolism*" was used for describing this process and expanding the concept to include dehalogenation reactions frequently carried out by microbial species.^{3,8}

It is decisive, if certain organic compound increases or decreases endogenous respiration of the test organism. For example, many hydrocarbons may, in some way, increase the endogenous respiration of the microbe cells without being oxidized. In this case it deals with the stimulation of respiration rather than the co-metabolism. The proof of disappearance of substrate and accumulation of end-products is required to clearly demonstrate a co-metabolic process. Further I would consider mainly the cases in which organic compound *decreases endogenous respiration of microorganism.*^{1,0}

These reactions take place also in pure cell dispersions of microorganisms after separating from nutrient medium and sometimes even with cell-less microbe homogenates. In such reactions it doesn't deal with co-metabolism, which evidently supposes the simultaneous metabolism course of other compounds and it is bound to certain growth phase of microbe. It is possible also with resting cells to carry out the experiments for the *enzyme induction*. In some cases, of course, especially in multistep-transformations it deals with the complex-processes. The microbial transformations of organic compounds are often stereospecific and therefore could be used favorably on the field of *preparative organic chemistry* and drug preparation,^{1,2,0,3,6,1,0,3,9,5,2} further for *chemotaxonomy* in the classification of some microbes and fungi^{5,6, \}

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Oxidative Processes :

- Oxidations of alcohol groups to keto groups
- Oxidations of aldehydes to carboxylic acids
- Hydroxylations of carbon chains or in ring
- Dehydrogenations of carbon chain or ring
(Formation of new double bond or aromatization)
- Cleavage of carbon chains or rings

Reduction Processes :

- Reduction of keto or aldehyde group.
- Hydrogenations of double bonds.

Hydrolytic or esterification reactions :

- Acetylations,
- Phosphorylations.
- Hydrolysis of amids.

Fig. 1. Types of microbial transformations of organic compounds

Metabolic transformations, such as oxidation, reduction or hydrolysis, usually result in the introduction of a new functional group, which decreases the toxicity. In this way, drugs and other foreign compounds may be deactivated—*detoxicated*.^{4,9} Detoxication is a decrease

in toxicity of certain foreign compounds. It is important to say that the conception of toxicity is very relative ; (it depends on the doses) and our indication : "foreign compound" is quite inexact. For bacterial populations there exist in reality no "foreign" organic compounds ; their inductive enzymatic systems are capable under suitable conditions to transform whatever organic matter. Obviously we don't know in advance in which direction the transformation will be passing through in using of a certain microorganism.^{5,5} There is very often different lag-period and also the whole kinetics of the transformation. The microbial cells show a considerably more pronounced enzymatic adaptation ability than animal cells^{3,7} ; the discovered transformation types of organic compound have resulted rather of empirims than of planned purpose : for example to make a certain strain perform a definite conversion in a definite organic substrate. The findings are often the result of a systematic selection and pure empirism, only.

The yeasts are very interesting objects for these transformations of organic compounds. Many carbonyl compounds are reduced to corresponding alcohols. According to Neuberg, optically active *phenylacetylcarbinol* is formed, together with benzyl alcohol, during fermentation of a sugar medium by *Saccharomyces* in the presence of benzaldehyde. A series of parallels can be drawn between the biosynthesis of acetone and of this key-intermediate in large-scale preparation of

The concept of a carbanion intermediate (ylid formation) for the action of *thismino pyrophosphate* in its enzymic reaction has greatly facilitated the understanding of the chemical role of this coenzyme

carbanion intermediate by thiazole ring

Fig. 2. Microbial transformation of benzaldehyde by *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*.

1-ephedrine and dex-phenmetrazine²⁷. We have studied yeast enzymatic reactions for this biosynthesis^{25,31,32}. The most important factor is the presence of yeast decarboxylase, which converts pyruvic acid to activated acetaldehyde³⁰. It was found, that thiamine and thiamine diphosphate (coenzyme of carboxylase) stimulated the formation of carbon dioxide in fermentation. In the given concentrations, which were 10-100 times higher than the normal level in yeast, it did not directly influence the biosynthesis of phenylacetyl-carbinol. The increased concentration of some physiological carbonyl compounds in fermentation medium decreases the reduction of benzaldehyde and then the yields of phenylacetylcarbinol are considerably higher. This process allowed the largescale production of 1-ephedrine in our country with the yield of 1 kg ephedrine from 2-2.5 kg of benzaldehyde.

Marsheck and Miyano⁴⁸ (Searle Lab. Chicago) proved recently the stereoselective hydrolysis of esters of racemic substituted n-heptanoic acid the key-intermediate in the total synthesis of natural prostaglandins and their analogues. In *steroid* series many oxo-substances were transformed with yeasts to corresponding alcohols, for example: androstenedione to testosterone, oestrone to oestradiol. In the course of chemical reduction it is possible that both epimers (alpha. and beta-) could be formed, whereas during yeast enzyme reduction only beta-epimer is produced.

In our institute we have further concentrated our attention on microbial oxidations of some *sugars* and their derivatives. Oxidative fermentations of sugars have in our country a long tradition, connected with name of Professor Bernhauer^{2,3}. Especially the

Fig. 3. Microbial transformation of pentitol and hexitols.

As a side product of dehydrogenation of sorbitol to sorbose, D-threo-2,6-dihexulose (5-oxo-D-fructose, or 5-oxo-L-sorbose) was isolated⁴⁰. Further dehydrogenations of aldonic acids were realized in connection with the studies of new approaches to vitamin C production besides well known Reichstein synthesis^{41,45}. Newer procedures usually use calcium 5-oxo-D-gluconate as an intermediate, which is prepared by fermentation of glucose in the presence of calcium carbonate. By catalytic hydrogenation the mixture of D-gluconate^(VI) and L-idonate^(IV) (in relation 1:1) is obtained from

We have examined the oxidation of 17-epimeric androstene-3,17-diols²⁶ by means of cells of *Penicillium notatum* and *Actinomyces globisporus*. In the first case the secondary alcohol group is oxidized in position 3 into respective 3-keto-derivative, while no oxidation occurs in position 17, neither in the configuration of hydroxyl 17 alpha nor in 17 beta. Out of this transformation there resulted either testosterone or its 17 alpha-epimer, according to starting steroid. Using the cells of *Actinomyces globisporus*, both positions 3 and 17 were oxidized when the starting steroid had the

3 β , 17 α -diol: R₁=H, R₂=OH

3 β , 17 β -diol: R₁=OH, R₂=H

Fig. 7. Microbial dehydrogenation and isomeration of epimeric androstenediols

which only the idonate component leads (by dehydrogenation in the position 2) to vitamin C^(VI). Both acids could be divided either as cadmium salts or better by fermentation, where L-idonate is transformed to 2-keto-L-idonic acid, whereas D-gluconate is decomposed. The similar process was published in the same year (1953) by Japanese author Yamazaki. Some of dehydrogenation processes in the sugar series represent examples of complex fermentations, where a part of sugar substrate is used for the growth of microorganism.

The most extensive application of microbial transformations is evident on the field of steroid chemistry^{1,4,15,23,35}. Microbial transformation of steroids nowadays offer a valuable tool in the preparation of a series otherwise difficultly accessible steroid compounds. Nowadays there are several monographs on this field and many reviews from various viewpoints, summarizing the findings. Ten years ago we published our experiences also in the monographs^{1,6}.

configuration of hydroxyls beta (that is: *cis*) and there resulted androstenedione on the one hand, and 17 alpha-epitestosterone on the other hand. When the starting steroids had configuration alpha (that is: *trans*) in position 3, there occurred no oxidation in this position even in this case.

Many oxidative microbes transformed *dehydroepiandrosterone* in androstenedione, similarly androstene-3 beta, 17 beta-diol can also be converted by means of microbial enzymes by a procedure analogous to the Oppenauer oxidation into *testosterone* as well as the corresponding 17 alpha-methyl derivative into methyltestosterone. Using the species *Penicillium notatum* the production of testosterone from progesterone with a yield of over 60% was made possible²⁴. In an analogous way progesterone derivatives possessing oxygen function in position 11, can be converted into corresponding androstene derivatives; yields were in these cases lower than with progesterone.

By help of the species *Corynebacterium simplex* it was possible to carry out the *aromatization* of 19-nortestosterone also directly into oestrogens by a microbial procedure. Many oxidative microbes transform further pregnenolone to *progesterone* analogously to the case of androgens.

adrenal cortex hormones and their analogues⁹⁹. When in the year 1952 Peterson published the fundamental findings that some microbial strains of order Mucorales, similarly to adrenal cortex cells, can also hydroxylate steroid molecule in *position 11*, a new way was opened for the preparation of corticoids of the cortisone type.

Fig. 8. Microbial transformations of progesterone

The microbial conversions of steroids however were extensively used especially in partial synthesis of the By help of the strain *Rhizopus nigricans* it was possible to obtain from progesterone its 11 alpha-hydroxy

Fig. 9. Microbial oxidation of cortisolone

derivative with a yield of up over 90%. This intermediate further served as raw-material in the synthesis of cortisone.

In our experiments with 11 beta-hydroxylation of steroids we examined 64 different strains and found the required hydroxylation in 45 cases. Using the species *Absidia orchidis* the metabolites of cortisolone (Steroid S) were: Cortisol, 11 alpha-epimer and in a small quantity also cortisone²⁸. 11 alpha-hydroxylation proceeds generally with higher yields than the 11 beta-hydroxylation. It was possible to obtain a mixture of both epimers in ration approximately 1:1 from the starting cortisolone. For the production of cortisone we now hydroxylate cortisolone by the species *Beauveria bassiana* to epicortisol with 95% yield¹⁴.

Analogously further 16 alpha-hydroxylations of corticoids were attempted, namely by help of different *Streptomyces* and *Actinomyces*⁵⁴. Though in a number of oestrogens the introduction of hydroxyl into position 16 alpha lowers the activity, the substituent in

position 16 in corticoids raises the effect especially combination with fluorine in position 9 alpha.

Further increase in the glucocorticoid activity with simultaneous limitation of mineralotropic effect was obtained by introduction another double bond into position 1-2 of the ring A in corticoids. We have followed this dehydrogenation in 248 different strains of microbes with cortisone as the starting steroid. In all strains carrying out dehydrogenation in position 1-2 we have also found the ability of reducing the 20-keto group into the corresponding 20 beta-hydroxyderivative.³³ There were considerable differences in the transformation rate among the individual strains, which had been examined. The most suitable qualities in this regard were shown by the strain *Mycobacterium flavum*¹³, which under suitable conditions gave a yield of up to over 80% prednisone from cortisone. By means of *Bacillus repens* we then succeeded to obtain 80% of prednisone without simultaneous formation of 20 beta-hydroxyderivative.

Fig. 10. 1, 2-Dehydrogenation of cortisone.

Fig. 11. Microbial 1-dehydrogenation and cleavage of steroids

Oxidative changes in different positions of the steroid skeleton frequently serve as initial steps for a further *splitting* of the individual steroid rings. From C. Joshi was found that the initial steps of steroid degradation are dehydrogenation in position 1-2 and hydroxylation in position 9 alpha, followed by the splitting of ring B.

On the figure there is the course of dehydrogenation of cortisone to prednisone,¹³ formation of 20 beta-hydroxy derivative and seco-derivatives in relation to time of fermentation. Concentrations in % of starting steroid were plotted against time of fermentation in hours.

Fig. 12. Time course of the conversion of cortisone to prednisone.

Fig. 13. Microbial oxidation of progesterone

In our studies of steroid transformations catalyzed by enzymic systems of lower fungi, twelve different reaction types, independent of external conditions, were found. These transformations may serve as one of the chemotaxonomic characteristics of the species or also of genera.^{5,6}

The existing classification of fungi is based mainly on morphological features. We described the attempts at a fast supplementary biochemical test which may be useful in identifying the microorganism tested. In many cases the classification into series and species of *Penicillium* according to morphological features coincides with the type of transformation reaction of the series. During a systematic investigation of the ability of different microorganisms to perform oxidative transformations of the steroid skeleton, attention was concentrated on various representatives of the genus *Fusarium* (1960)^{1,2}, *Aspergillus* (1957)⁷ and *Penicillium* (1962)^{1,2}. A total of 191 strains of 94 *Penicillium* species was evaluated.

genation in some members of the genera *Penicillium* and *Aspergillus*. In the later reaction hydroxylation occurs in position 15 alpha. We have studied a large series of strains of the genus *Fusarium* (98 strains, 24 species and eleven variants)^{1,2} and six different steroids as substrates. Only three species (*Fusarium lateritium*, *F. solani* and *F. Caucasicum*) were characteristic for splitting-off of progesterone side chain, all others were hydroxylating in positions 6 beta and 15 alpha. The end-product of breakdown in the first type is testololactone or its 1-dehydro derivative.

Cleavage of the side chain of progesterone at C₁₇ giving rise to testolactone⁶ as the end product was the most frequent as it was demonstrated in 105 strains of 44 species of genus *Penicillium*^{1,2}. Intermediary products of the reaction were delta⁴-androstene-3,17-dione and testosterone. A similar type of reaction was also encountered in many species of the genus *Aspergillus*. In no case could the formation of a double bond in position 1-2 be demonstrated, as in the case

Fig. 14. Oxidations of progesterone with *Penicillium* and *Aspergillus*

When studying and evaluating the transformation properties of certain strains of genus *Fusarium* in steroid molecules, two basic types of reaction were found. In the first, the side chain of pregnane steroids was broken down, accompanied by dehydrogenation of the steroid skeleton in position 1-2. Progesterone, for example, is transformed in this way to delta⁴-androstadiene-3,17-dione. Breakdown of the side chain of pregnane steroid was also found, without dehydro-

with some species of the genus *Fusarium*. Cleavage of progesterone giving rise to testosterone as the end product was found only in 14 strains of 5 species, hydroxylation in position 11 alpha in 6 strains of 3 species, and in position 15 beta in 5 strains of 2 species only. Though Dulaney affirmed that the hydroxylation of progesterone in the position 15 is a very frequent reaction with different species, it was not possible to demonstrate this hydroxylation in the 15 alpha at all.

Classification of aspergilli (Raper & Fennell-1965) and types of steroid transformation (Hanc-1965)

Aspergillus	Transformation Type	Aspergillus	Transformation Type
A. clavatus	11 alpha-OH	A. flavus	cleavage
A. glaucus	cleavage	A. wentii	11 alpha-OH
ornatus	11 alpha-OH	cremeus	11 alpha-OH
cervinus	?	sparsus	?
restrictus	15 beta-OH	versicolor	11-a 15-OH
fumigatus	15 beta-OH	nidulans	11 alpha-OH
ochraceus	11 alpha-OH	ustus	11 alpha-OH
niger	11 alpha-OH	flavipes	cleavage
candidus	15 beta-OH	terreus	cleavage

11 alpha-OH : A. clavatus, A. ornatus, A. ochraceus, A. niger, A. wentii, A. cremeus, A. Nidulans, A. Ustus

15 beta-OH : A. restrictus, A. fumigatus, A. candidus

Cleavage : A. glaucus, A. flavus, A. flavipes, A. terreus

Fig 15. Classification of Aspergill.

the same transformations of the steroid skeleton as enzymes of animal origin. In some cases microbial enzymes have been found to carry out further transformations that have not been proved with enzymes of animal cells.

It is apparent that there is no significant phylogenic development of the metabolic transformations reactions. Some of these reactions, for example the 7-hydroxylation of coumarin, are strongly evident in some mammals, absent in others, and yet are found in insects and other lower orders of the animal kingdom. In fact, the greatest versatility in biotransformations is shown by the simplest of organisms, the bacteria.

further studies by Lawrence (1966) and Singh⁵¹ Vézina (1968)⁵³ on transformation of steroids have demonstrated the widespread and high activity of fungal spores and catabolic processes. During transformation, even though they are maintained in the early pregermination stage (before swelling takes place), spores are 3 to 10 times more active than mycelium on a dry weight basis. Although spores have only been used to transform steroids, fatty acids, triglycerides, sugars and penicillin, there is no reason to believe that they will not transform other substrates, such as alkaloids, drugs, hydrocarbons etc.

Enzyme induction *in spores* could not be observed²². The enzymes from spores appear to be *constitutive*⁵⁰.

Fig. 19. Sites in molecule of corticoid undergoing changes during the inactivating metabolism

Most species differences in the metabolism of foreign compounds are concerned with quantitative differences of the same mechanism⁴⁹. The quantitative differences in the metabolism are dependent on the reaction velocities of alternative metabolic pathways, which are determined principally by : relative concentration of the different detoxication enzymes, by the concentrations of coenzymes and allosteric effectors in microbial cells, further by physical and chemical nature of the foreign organic compound and by the amount of transformed compounds, which determines substrat concentration and reaction velocity of enzymic reactions, dependent on the reaction kinetics.

Very interesting transformations of organic compounds by *fungal spores* have been described⁵³. These cells, generally considered as a dormant stage in the life of fungi, have been shown to contain enzymes necessary for a variety of metabolic activities. More than sixty enzymes are now known to be common to cells and spores⁵⁰. It is therefore unlikely, that all spore proteins are uniquely different from their vegetative cell homologues. A more likely hypothesis is, that a single genome directs the synthesis of a given vegetative and spore enzyme protein. Enzymatically active proteins associated with dormant spores were stabilized in some manner by the spore structure and were intrinsically heat stable molecules.

Before the observation of Gehring and Knight (1958) spores had been primarily used for maintenance and inoculation purposes by the industrial microbiologist, and the possibility of using them for transformation of organic compounds had not been visualized. Even

The spores transformed the same substrate as the mycelial cells. It is interesting, that the steroid metabolizing activity of the spores dropped dramatically upon germination and disappeared completely from mycelia collected in the logarithmic or stationary phase of growth²².

The "spore process" is limited to sporulating fungi and streptomycetes. Feasibility of producing spores and transforming on a large scale has already been established^{51,53}. The use of spores offers certain advantages : It can be stored frozen for a long period of time without significant loss in activity and is readily available for transformation of organic compounds. Homogeneity of spore suspensions and simplicity of transformation media prevent excessive foaming and make also extractions easier.

Microbial transformations mainly for *drug and intermediate preparation* could compete with pure synthetic processes only in those cases, where they represent the selective reactions without side products and with high yields^{55,56}. Usually the transformations are provided in relatively low concentrations. It is therefore necessary to use large volumes, which makes the isolation procedures rather difficult. Even in laboratory scale *these methods are very useful*, especially for *stereochemical selective reactions*. The isolation of certain induced enzymes from microbial cells have occurred only rarely for the present. Some dehydrogenases and isomerases were isolated entirely in crystalline state, but hydroxylating systems showed to be multi-component and homogenisation of cells destroyed them.

Some microbial dehydrogenases were used for the analyses to distinguish the structure elements of compounds with very similar configuration.

Recently the preparation of *microbial enzymes* bound to non-soluble carriers of polymer structure has been studied. This complex-preparations are more stable and could be easily reactivated. Microbial enzymes bound in such a solid phase could be considered as a real reagent for organic synthesis and analysis.

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